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INVESTIGATING PECULIARITIES OF THE STRUCTURE OF CONFLICTOLOGICAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHERS: THEORETICAL PERSPECTIVES

The paper deals with investigation of different contemporary approaches to the structure of conflictological competences, in particular among the teachers of foreign languages and differentiation to professional characteristics and personal qualities of specialists in the structure of conflictological competence was given. At modern stage of the development of conflictology it is relevant to generalize scientific approaches to the structure of conflictological competence.

***The purpose of the article** is to analyze the structure of the notion «conflictological competence» in scientific literature; to highlight the structural components of conflictological competence as the factor of constant professional growth of the teachers.*

***Methodology** is based on psychological and pedagogical theories that reveal conceptual approaches to the essence of conflictological competence and its structure.*

***Scientific novelty** of the article explores the structure of conflictological competence as complex structurally functional system consisting of five connected components: cognitive; motivational; emotional-volitional; reflexive; behavioral.*

***Conclusions:** The main functions of conflictological competence of the teachers were summarized: informational; regulatory; optimizational; reflexive; prophylactic. The following factors of formation of conflictological competence were substantiated: communicative potential, self-regulatory and individual-typological. The following criteria for classifying and evaluating the characteristics of conflictological competence have been singled out: the level of conscious choice of behavioral strategies in conflict situation; the level of conscious understanding of the necessity of changing destructive conflict into a constructive one, the absence of conflictophobia, understanding the importance of conflictological competence for future teachers, the desire to master conflictological competence at the highest level to be able to resolve conflicts in pedagogical process.*

***Key words:** conflictological competence, the structure of conflictological competence, components, functions, criteria, teachers of foreign languages.*

Introduction. Relevance of the article. In contemporary world, it is almost axiomatic and no one will deny the fact that conflicts of various magnitudes occur frequently thus making conflict is a daily reality. Young people (especially schoolchildren and students) are especially vulnerable to stresses, emotional breakdowns etc. caused by daily conflicts. It means that all efforts of administration of high educational establishments and the teachers in secondary schools must be concentrated on their personal growth in the field of conflictology developing their conflictological competence and careful investigation of successful conflict management and conflict resolution techniques as education is a complex system that requires effective teamwork and cooperation to function well.

Analysis of recent research and publications. Recognition of conflictology as an important contemporary issue within pedagogy and psychology is proved by widespread research activity, but also by the publications of several dissertations reflecting one theoretical perspective or another, and by the attention increasingly given to the subject in scientific articles on the typology of conflicts, nature of conflicts, and the availability of monographs devoted to conflictology (I. Vashchenko, M. Klyap, L. Dolisnka and L. Matyash-Zayatz, T. Dutkevitch, A. Girnuk, N. Grishina, Z. Kovalchuk, T. Korotkina, M. Leonov, N. Mikitenko, I. Soroka and others). Yet, despite the existence of authoritative research papers, there is to date no book-length account of conflictological competence, its structure of the various theoretical currents which inform present-day pedagogical studies, nor one which takes account of the associated disciplines, such as social studies, psychology etc., to which those studies are making such a vital contribution.

Thus, **the purpose of the paper** is to present systematic analysis of different scientific approaches to the structure of conflictological competences from the viewpoint of their theoretical point-by-point description.

Methodology. The following theoretical methods to attain the purpose of the study are used: comparative analysis of scientific literature to investigate the approaches to the structure of conflictological competence; classification and generalization.

Results of the article. As far as our investigation is concerned we must admit that nowadays there is no universally accepted formal classification of the structure of conflictological competence nor a proposal for their uniform and systematic treatment in scientific literature, so in the scope of pedagogy there is no agreed approach among scientists as for the structure of conflictological competence [14, 316]. The detailed analysis of the numerous scientific works (E. Bogdanova, A. Derkach, O. Denisova and V. Zazikina) gives us ground to substantiate the following components of conflictological competence: gnostic component (the knowledge about the reasons of the conflicts, peculiarities of its development, psychological characteristics of conflict persons); regulative component (the ability to exert influence on the opponents, the ability to organize the work in post conflict situation); communicative component (the usage of communicative tactics aiming to avoid conflicts); constructive component (the ability to predict the behavior of the participants of the conflict for further planning of one's own actions); reflexive status component (the ability of reflexion of one's own behavior) and normative component (the knowledge of professional ethical norm of behavior) [3, 17; 4, 157-158].

This interpretation of the structure of conflictological competence includes components corresponding to the conception of I. Nikulina and N. Solovjeva distinguishing nearly the same components of conflictological competence of the teachers of higher educational establishments: gnostic; constructive; regulatory; reflexive status component; normative component and communicative [13, 96-97]; A. Mityaeva also sticks to structuring conflictological competence according to the following components: gnostic, regulatory or constructive, reflexive status and normative [11, 274].

In general the data obtained indicate that the majority of scientists (O. Denisov, A. Derkach, V. Ghukovsky, V. Mityaeva, I. Nikulina and others) support the position of differentiating the following components in the structure of conflictological competence: gnostic, regulatory or constructive, communicative, reflexive status, normative. These and other researchers use the above-mentioned structure of conflictological competence as a whole or may somehow change it.

Consideration must be given to the thought of three componential structure of conflictological competence (G. Bereghna, O. Klimentjeva, I. Soroka, I. Titarenko and others) which is viewed as a unity of content (the system of scientific knowledge about conflicts and ways of their successful resolution), activity (skills of behavior in conflict situations) and personal sphere (motivation, reflexion, empathy, emotional resistance, flexible behavior in conflicts). I. Soroka describes the following components of conflictological competence: cognitive (the knowledge of the theory, understanding and perception of pedagogical conflict), emotional (negative or positive emotions prevailing in the process of pedagogical interaction and the ability of the teacher to manage them) and behavioral (the high level of conflict resistance and cooperation of teachers in conflict situations) [17, 297-298]. This approach has much in common with investigation of N. Isaeva and M. Chudaeva considering that these components allow resolving conflicts effectively thus helping the personal growth and self-realization of the participants of the conflict [7, 157].

Three main blocks in the structure of conflictological competence of the teachers of secondary schools: axiological component (the system of qualities characterizing personality); informational component and operational component were highlighted by G. Bereghna, L. Aleksandrova, A. Munshi where axiological component has invariant structure fulfilling regulative function (motivational, emotional, and volitional) for effective conflict management; informational and operational components include invariant part (skills and knowledge necessary in all spheres of impact on conflict) and differentiated part (skills and knowledge necessary for realization of each sphere of impact on conflict) [1, 183; 2, 22].

It should be noted here that structural dynamic model of conflictological competence worked out by N. Leonov is based on the assumption that there are three groups of teachers with low, middle and high levels of potential in managing conflict situations according to the following structural components: cognitive (presupposes the ability of a person to analyze conflict situation, one's behavior in it), motivational (presupposes the orientation of the person to resolve conflicts constructively, to demonstrate diplomatic qualities); regulative (means the ability of the person to demonstrate self-management of one's emotional and volitional state in preconflict and conflict situations) [8].

So, within the scope of pedagogy the three-componential structure of conflictological competence is considered the most widely accepted. Though several scientists (I. Matiykiv, V. Sherniyazova, L. Yaroslav and others) stress that there are more components in the structure of the phenomenon under analysis where motivational aspect plays the important role. As pointed out by I. Matiykiv such functionally connected components of conflictological competence are singled out: motivational-evaluative (reveals the general tendency to build partnership relations and motivation to resolve conflicts preserving these relations), cognitive (connected with conflictological literacy), communicative (helps to organize constructive dialogue among the participants of the conflict), reflexive and emotional-volitional (self-regulation in the process of productive conflict management, volitional realization of knowledge, skills, experience and values) [10].

Some scientists are convinced that conflictological competence of the future teacher is complex structurally functional system consisting of five connected components: *cognitive* including the system of

scientific knowledge about different aspects of the phenomenon of conflict; *motivational* i.e. the absence of conflictophobia, the orientation of a person to constructive resolution of conflict; *emotional-volitional* component that defines the ability of a person to control his emotional state in conflict situations; *reflexive* denoting the ability of a person to investigate one's own psychological potential and skills of reconstructing the psychological portraits of his opponents; *behavioral* supposing a wide spectrum of strategies and tactics of behavior in conflict situations and their adequate usage [18, 143].

The differentiation between professional characteristics and personal qualities of specialists in the structure of conflictological competence were given by L. Mychina. The author focuses on two blocks in the structure of conflictological competence, noting that professional characteristics and personal qualities are important. Personal qualities of the teacher include: reflexion of one's own behavior (the analysis of behavior before the conflict, during the conflict and in post-conflict situation), empathy (understanding and sympathy to the opponent), emotional flexibility (the ability to restore one's emotional state in post-conflict situation and control one's emotions in conflict situation), pedagogical tact (compliance to the norms of the behavior of the teacher), creativity (search for new ways of resolving conflict), self-development (the ability self-improvement), self-analysis (rethinking of one's behavior and feelings in conflict and post conflict situations), openness (sincere emotions and thoughts), spirituality (high level of self-organization). Block of professional characteristic includes: theoretical knowledge of the conflict, the knowledge the rules of corporative behavior, the normative documents of educational establishment, the knowledge of the methods of organization of educational activity, practical skills of constructive conflict resolution situations, skills of predicting conflict situations [12, 144-145].

Many academic publications in the field of conflictological competence are focused on characterization of each structural component of conflictological competence as the choice of the criteria for classifying and evaluating the characteristics of certain phenomena is an obligatory condition of any research and depends on the authors' positions of scientists. Thus, different criteria and criterial significatives are used. Suggested criteria are decomposed in corresponding criterial significatives that presuppose the total of certain qualities and requirements. These criteria are chosen by scientists that is why they may differ in the process of investigating conflictological competence. N. Dzaraeva, for instance, has used the following criteria for defining the levels of conflictological competence: the amount of theoretical knowledge as for the psychological nature of conflict, its structure and dynamics, types, possible reasons and effective ways of solution; emotional state of a person in conflict situation; the system of practical skills of handling conflicts in a collaborative way [5, 101].

The following criteria of formation of conflictological competence were differentiated by S. Romanov: the level of conscious choice of behavioral strategies in conflict situation; the level of conscious understanding of the necessity of changing destructive conflict into a constructive one, the absence of conflictophobia, understanding the importance of conflictological competence for future teachers, the desire to master conflictological competence at the highest level to be able to resolve conflicts in pedagogical process [15, 59].

In our work we stick to the point of the scientists (I. Vashchenko, M. Klyap, S. Romanov, T. Saraliev and others) that the components of the structure of conflictological competence fulfil certain functions and have certain spheres of application. There are the following main functions of conflictological competence of the teacher pointed out by scientists: *informational* (singling out the positive aspects of conflict and evaluation of information), *regulatory* (the teacher as a mediator in conflicts); *optimizational* (the ability to use different strategies for minimization of destructive forms of conflict), *reflexive* (the reconstruction of difficulties in conflicts and investigation of its reasons); *prophylactic* (minimization of tension between conflict participants) [16, 334; 15, 57-58].

Besides, the factors of formation of conflictological competence worked out by E. Lopes and K. Oliferova are worth mentioning. The authors consider the following: communicative potential, self-regulatory and individual-typological. *Communicative potential* defines the ability of the student for communication, the need for sincere and open interaction with surrounding people. *Self-regulatory* factor determines the ability for tolerant perception of social and cultural differences, for careful attitude to historical heritage and cultural traditions; skills of differentiating the emotions of other people and the ability to influence their emotional state; determination of a person to constructive conflict resolution. The third factor individual-typological characteristics of the graduate includes the dependence from the influence of stress-factors of casual life situations and is based on self-assurance, being an optimist, active and emotionally stable in stress situations [9, 83]. We consider that these factors have an impact on the formation of conflictological competence of future teachers of foreign languages. Special attention must be paid to communicative potential of young teachers, which presupposes trustworthy and open interaction with people of different nationalities speaking foreign languages. Finding common ground with these people, understanding them decreases the possibility of conflict situations in society as well as in education sphere.

Taking into account the main functions and factors of formation of conflictological competence of the teachers and different approaches for structuring the investigated definition in our research its componential composition has been determined where functions correlate with the structure while the factors define the main index of the investigated phenomenon: cognitive-reflexive component, motivational-evaluative component, operational–corrective component.

Mentioned above the components of the structure of conflictological competence correlate with the following criteria of investigated phenomenon:

Availability of conflictological knowledge and skills: evaluative-prognostic (correct appreciation of the situation and the ability to foresee the development of conflict); gnostic (adequate diagnosis of the structure and reasons of conflict, differentiating objective and subjective reasons of conflict, finding correct ways of solving conflict situation); communicative (perception of the inner state of a person, dialogic speech);

Formation of positive motivation (self-improvement, positive attitude to people, involvement in conflictology), personal– professional qualities (reflexion, tact, tolerance, emotional stability, communication skills);

Availability of certain behavioral forms and strategies of conflict resolution (competition, avoidance, compromise, cooperation).

Conclusions. To conclude, we can state that fruitful and careful examination of contemporary psychological-pedagogical literature revealed the components and criteria of the structure of conflictological competence of future teachers. This article cannot pretend to explore in any depth such area as the structure of conflictological competence, but it seems worth working out the model of formation of conflictological competence of future teachers of foreign languages based on individual strategy of behavior of each participant of educational process in the system of higher education.

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ТЕОРЕТИЧНІ ПЕРСПЕКТИВИ ДОСЛІДЖЕННЯ СТРУКТУРИ КОНФЛІКТОЛОГІЧНОЇ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТІ МАЙБУТНІХ УЧИТЕЛІВ ІНОЗЕМНИХ МОВ

У статті проаналізовано сучасні підходи до класифікації структури конфліктологічної компетентності майбутніх учителів іноземних мов та представлено релевантну диференціацію професійних характеристик та особистісних якостей спеціаліста в структурі конфліктологічної компетентності. На сучасному етапі розвитку конфліктології вважаємо аналіз структури конфліктологічної компетентності вчителів іноземної мов актуальним.

Мета статті полягає в аналізі структури категорії «конфліктологічна компетентність» у науковій літературі; уточненні змістовної та структурної складової конфліктологічної компетентності як одного із напрямів неперервного професійного зростання вчителів.

Методологічною основою статті є психологічні, педагогічні теорії та положення, які розкривають концептуальні підходи щодо досліджуваної проблематики.

Наукова новизна полягає у розкритті структури конфліктологічної компетентності як складною функціональної системи, що складається з п'яти взаємопов'язаних елементів: когнітивного, мотиваційного, емоційно-вольового, рефлексивного, поведінкового.

Висновки. Підсумовано основні функції конфліктологічної компетентності учителя: інформаційна, регуляторна, оптимізаційна, рефлексивна та профілактична; визначено фактори, що впливають на формування конфліктологічної компетентності учителя: комунікативний потенціал, саморегуляція і індивідуально-типологічний; з'ясовано та описано критерії для класифікації та оцінювання характеристик конфліктологічної компетентності: рівень свідомого розуміння необхідності переводу деструктивного конфлікту у конструктивне русло, відсутність конфліктофобії, розуміння важливості конфліктологічної компетентності для майбутніх учителів, бажання оволодіти цією компетентністю на найвищому рівні задля вирішення конфліктів у педагогічному процесі.

Ключові слова: конфліктологічна компетентність, структура конфліктологічної компетентності, компоненти, функції, критерії, учителі іноземної мови.

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